

IMPROVEMENT OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF "DAKA- TEX" LLC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10031317>

Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of marketing principles, determining the main directions and indicators of marketing analysis, developing ways to improve marketing analysis in manufacturing enterprises, product production and customer service.*

Key words: *enterprise, customer service, demand, efficiency, realization, competition.*

Introduction. The economic reforms carried out in our country open the door to wide opportunities for production enterprises. As a result of the benefits and preferences given to them, the increase of funds at the disposal of enterprises, the introduction of new forces and the increase of the welfare of the population serve. It is certainly gratifying to see such positive changes in our economy and the economic activity of the country. However, today we all know well that the market economy is an economic system that operates within the framework of the influence of a complex of competition and so-called struggles. In this system, some enterprises cooperate with each other, and similar enterprises are in constant competition. In their economic activities, they always adapt to the demand of the time, more precisely, to the demand of the market, and produce and sell various goods.

State support plays a decisive role in increasing the competitiveness of enterprises in Uzbekistan. The government has implemented policies to support the development of various sectors such as textiles, agriculture and manufacturing. For example, the government has established textile clusters to support the development of the textile industry. The state also provided financial support to farmers to increase the production of agricultural products.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing activities and their practical application, including F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. .We can include famous scientists like Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

At the same time, it should be mentioned that the methodological work on the practical application of theoretical developments and their application in enterprises is insufficient. In order to apply the theoretical recommendations in practice, it is necessary for each enterprise to draw from its own experience, conduct relevant scientific research and develop recommendations and systems for the implementation of the theory.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results The purpose of the study is to determine the methods of applying marketing principles in effective management of "Daka-Tex" LLC.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved in the research:

- Importance of marketing principles in modern management theory;
- Revealing the content of the analytical function in marketing activities;
- Determining the main directions and indicators of marketing analysis;
- Analyzing the marketing activity of the selected enterprise;
- Development of ways to improve marketing analysis in production enterprises.

Marketing principles are a condition, a requirement that reveals the basis of marketing and its essence. The essence of marketing is the production of goods and service to the consumer, always targeting the possibilities of demand generation to the market demand. The following basic principles come from the essence of marketing:

- it is necessary to produce what consumers need;
- working in the market not with the offer of goods and services, but with the means of solving the problems of consumers;
- it is necessary to organize the production of goods after researching the need and demand;
- strengthening the firm's concentration on the final results of production - export activity;
- using a comprehensive approach and targeted program method to achieve the set goals, which leads to the formation of a marketing program based on the use of marketing concept tools;
- in order to cover all stages of the transfer of goods to the consumer with marketing, at the same time, on the basis of targeted influence, to apply the strategy and tactics of the production of goods corresponding to the market demand;
- targeting the long-term perspective of effective communication based on the prediction of the behavior of goods in the market and the implementation of strategic planning of the enterprise's activities and marketing services;

An important part of marketing analysis is the analysis of economic and financial indicators. "Daka-Tex" LLC since it is an independent economic entity, its activity in the market should be expressed first of all by economic indicators. Therefore, we need to analyze the financial statements in order to find out whether management activities are organized in the enterprise.

Table 1

Analysis of the dynamics of changes in the composition of assets of the balance sheet of "DAKA-TEX" LLC during 2018-2022

Balance sheet asset	In early 2018	At the end of 2018	At the end of 2019	At the end of 2020	At the end of 2021	At the end of 2022
	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums
Total assets	26 230.91	29 134.35	33,088.29	37,974.40	40,696.23	52,815.78
1.1 Long-term assets	1 000.44	866.25	2 319.02	2 209.41	3,952.52	3 495.51
1.2 Current Assets	25 230.47	28 268.10	30,769.27	35,764.99	36,743.71	49 320.27
1.2.1 Inventory of raw materials	10,861.01	14,072.09	10,626.47	13,461.32	11,750.33	14 155.52

1.2.2 Future period costs	0.60	1 274.68	116.63	20.74	0.00	0.02
1.2.3 General debtors	10,954.55	8,728.27	19,822.14	21 156.91	21 332.64	35,040.40
1.2.4 Value in monetary form	3 414.31	4 193.06	204.03	1 026.02	3 570.74	24,33

According to the results of the financial analysis, "DAKA-TEX" LLC pays great attention to financial strength in its activities. This can be seen from the results of the financial policy, which have been high in the last four years.

Analyzing the marketing activities of "Daka-Tex" LLC, we must consider its marketing complex policy.

The main structural element of the marketing complex, the initial stage of its development is the formation and implementation of the product (product) policy of the organization (enterprise).

The main products produced at "Daka-Tex" LLC:

- 1) thread
- 2) is a knitted fabric.

Yarn products Production and packaging are carried out entirely on the basis of European technologies. The enterprise produces two types of yarn products, Ne 20/1 and Ne 30/1. an average of 9 tons per day, and 250-300 tons of products are produced every month. The enterprise warehouse has a large stock of kalava in its warehouse, which guarantees constant availability and uninterrupted supply to its partners. When packing yarn, 24 pieces of yarn are placed in 1 box. The weight of 1 kalava is 2 kg 150 g.

LLC "Daka-Tex" JKhas a lot of experience and a professional team in the production of knitted fabric. The knitting shop is equipped with Pilotelli (Italy), Pailung (Taiwan) and Leadsfon (China) circular knitting machines, and Boosan (China) flat knitting machines. The presence of circular knitting machines with one and two rings allows this company to produce all types of knitted fabrics. Knitted fabrics are made of natural cotton, elastane and mixed yarns.

Kulirnaya glad- this is the thinnest of cotton knitted fabrics, it is woven from 100% cotton or with the addition of lycra. Kulirnaya gladis well stretched in the transverse direction. Knitted clothes made from it are very light and comfortable, they are used for the production of various clothes: children's and adults' underwear, T-shirts, pajamas, polo shirts, tourism clothes, special clothes, etc.

The name of this knitted fabric is related to the unique weave of the thread. Translated from English, interlock means overlapping, crossing. The interlock looks the same on both sides. It is a very soft, silky and at the same time durable cotton knitted fabric, it practically does not stretch, so it is often used for sewing children's clothes and underwear. Very comfortable pajamas, nightgowns, T-shirts, etc. are made from it. Interlock is knitted on a bed of two needles fixed at a certain angle on special knitting machines.

Pique is a dense cotton knitted fabric, the main distinguishing feature of which is the texture of the front surface in the form of honeycomb patterns. The pique is also woven from 100% cotton and lycra. Pique is widely used in sewing popular clothes such as polo shirts.

These knitted fabrics are named so because of a special weave, in which the lining thread is tied from the reverse side down, forming its structure, and treated with additional wool. Footer- this is an excellent heat-protecting and abrasion-resistant knitted fabric. Footer used in sewing warm products: sweaters, caps, sports suits, robes, pajamas and products for children, teenagers and adults.

Ribbana is a knitted fabric with a corrugated structure in small strips. Due to its elasticity, ribana is often used for cuffs and collars, and is also used in the production of children's and adult clothing. Ribana clothing absorbs moisture well and does not lose its shape. Ribana can be made of 100% cotton or with the addition of lycra, which significantly increases its elasticity.

Kashkorse- this is a very elastic knitted fabric with a large elastic band structure. Kashkorse is made from both 100% cotton and lycra added, which increases its elasticity and makes it suitable for use in the production of clothing items such as necklines and sleeve cuffs. Kashkorse is also widely used in the production of outerwear, children's clothes, etc.

"Daka-Tex" LLC independently defines the price policy development scheme based on the goals and objectives of the enterprise's development, organizational structure and management methods, traditions established in the enterprise, and economic and financial indicators. It can be influenced by factors such as the level of production costs and others as internal factors, as well as the state and development of the business environment as external factors.

LLC "Daka-Tex" JSC is one of the most advanced and largest full-cycle factories in Uzbekistan, which cooperates with large federal clothing retailers in Russia and the CIS countries. is engaged in the delivery of knitted fabrics and dyed knitted fabrics to Russia, Italy, Turkey, China and other countries.

In addition, "Daka-Tex" LLC has many years of experience on the basis of orders and has been delivering customers' orders with quality and on time. To him for many years Gloria Jeans, MODIS, Vse Mikey, Wildberries, Oodji, Detsky mir, STAN, Teximport, Coca-Cola, Vostok Servis, Ekspert Spetsodejda, Ashan, Profmax, TechnoAvia, Beeline and other companies have expressed their trust.

From the above information we can know that "Daka-Tex" LLC has also paid great attention to the marketing promotion and communication policy in relation to its customers and partners.

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